

The bolometric-hemispherical emissivity

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1 Introduction

This text has been compiled from the Ph.D. thesis of Kay Wohlfarth [Wohlfarth, 2025]. It derives the equations of the bolometric-hemispherical emissivity $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ and investigates how this quantity behaves for the Moon and Mercury, providing valuable insights for thermal modeling activities.

2 General Theory

Planck's radiation law links the equilibrium temperature T of an ideal non-reflecting body, a blackbody, to its emitted diffuse spectral specific intensity $I_b(T, \lambda)$. After several attempts to formalize blackbody radiation with classical physics, Planck [1900] made the first viable theoretical treatment. In an ad-hoc fashion, Planck replaced the assumption of a continuous energy distribution with discrete energy levels, later recognized as the birth of quantum mechanics. Mandel and Wolf [1995] work with a modern formalism to derive blackbody radiation that will not be treated here for brevity. Planck's law is defined as

$$U(T, \lambda) = \frac{2\pi h_0 c_0^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{h_0 c_0 / \lambda k_B T} - 1}, \quad (1)$$

where $h_0 = 6.626 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg s}^{-1}$ is Planck's constant and $c_0 = 299.792 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is the speed of light. The diffuse spectral specific intensity (radiance) I_b emitted by a blackbody is

$$I_b(T, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\pi} U(T, \lambda). \quad (2)$$

Integrating over the upper half-space Ω and all wavelengths, the total power per area that leaves the blackbody becomes what is known as the Stefan-Boltzmann law

$$dP(T) = \int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \int_{\Omega} I_b(T, \lambda) \cos(e) d\Omega d\lambda dA \quad (3)$$

$$= \left(\frac{2\pi^5 k_B^4}{15c_0^2 h_0^3} \right) T^4 dA \quad (4)$$

$$= \sigma T^4 dA, \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma = 5.671 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-4}$ is termed the Stefan-Boltzmann constant and $d\Omega = \sin(e)ded\phi$ is the differential surface element in spherical coordinates. The blackbody is an idealized body that does not reflect but absorbs radiation at every wavelength. Such bodies do not exist in nature. The thermal emission of real bodies observed under the emission angle e is operationalized with the spectral directional emissivity ϵ_d such that the measured diffuse specific intensity of the actual body becomes

$$I(T, e, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\pi} \epsilon_d(e, \lambda) U(T, \lambda). \quad (6)$$

Consequently, the power per area that leaves a real body with nonzero emissivity is defined as

$$dP(T) = \int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_d(e, \lambda) \cos(e) I_b(T, \lambda) d\Omega d\lambda dA \quad (7)$$

$$= \frac{\int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\epsilon_d(e, \lambda)}{\pi} \cos(e) I_b(T, \lambda) d\Omega d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} I_b(T, \lambda) d\lambda} \int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \pi I_b(T, \lambda) d\lambda dA \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{\int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_h(\lambda) I_b(T, \lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} I_b(T, \lambda) d\lambda} \int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \pi I_b(T, \lambda) d\lambda dA \quad (9)$$

$$= \bar{\epsilon}_h(T) \sigma T^4 dA, \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ is the bolometric hemispherical emissivity. In its most general form, $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ depends on the temperature, which affects the calculation of the equilibrium temperature and the brightness temperature of a planetary surface.

3 Behavior of the Bolometric-hemispherical emissivity

This section explores how the bolometric emissivity $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ of a planetary surface behaves for various silicate materials and illumination conditions. For simplicity, this section assumes a smooth surface at solar distance r illuminated under the solar incidence angle i . The surface is sheeted with a particulate silicate material with an isotropic but spectrally variant directional emissivity $\epsilon_d(\lambda)$. The temperature T and the bolometric emissivity $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ of the surface have the following mathematical relationship:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_h(T)\sigma T^4 = (1 - A_{\text{dh}}(i))\frac{S_0}{r^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{\epsilon}_h(T) = \frac{\int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_d(\lambda) \int_{\Omega} \cos(e)U(T, \lambda)d\Omega d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} U(T, \lambda)d\lambda}. \quad (12)$$

Both equations are coupled, i.e., T requires $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ and vice versa. A fixed-point iteration with $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 1$ as initialization converges after several steps and provides the solution for $\bar{\epsilon}_h$. The equations are solved for several emissivity spectra $\epsilon_d(\lambda)$, incidence angles from $i = 0 \dots 85^\circ$, and three different distances (Sun-Moon: $r = 1$ AU, Sun-Mercury perihelion $r = 0.30$ AU, and Sun-Mercury aphelion $r=0.46$ AU). The directional hemispherical albedo is computed according to Keihm [1984] with $A_{\text{dh}} = 0.12 + 0.03(i/45^\circ)^3 + 0.14(i/90^\circ)^8$. The computation crucially depends on the directional emissivity of the material. Unfortunately, no in-situ lunar emissivity spectra exist that are both reliable and cover a wavelength region from approximately 4–20 μm that allows computing $\bar{\epsilon}_h$. Therefore, the author considers the best available laboratory spectra. Salisbury et al. [1987] provide reflectance measurements of the Apollo samples that can be converted to emissivity via the Hapke model. Donaldson Hanna et al. [2017] present Apollo measurements under ambient and lunar conditions, but the spectra are not publicly available. Maturilli et al. [2008] measured the emissivity of several analog materials. For this analysis, the average lunar highland and lunar mare spectrum from Salisbury et al. [1987] and several mineral analog spectra from Maturilli et al. [2008] are considered.

3.1 Lunar case

Figure 1 (left) shows the spectral emissivity used for this study. Figure 1 (right) shows the bolometric-hemispherical emissivity of different minerals as a function of incidence angle at $r = 1$ AU. The values for $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ almost do not depend on the incidence angle for $i < 85^\circ$ at all. The observed emissivity values agree with the literature, which often assumes $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.90$ for asteroids and $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.95$ for

Figure 1. Left: Emissivity spectra of various minerals of a mixture of grain sizes taken from Maturilli et al. [2008] and averaged Apollo spectra derived from Salisbury et al. [1987]. Right: Bolometric-hemispherical emissivity $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ of a surface covered in regolith of various compositions. The surface is at $r=1$ AU away from the Sun and illuminated under different incidence angles i . $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ is almost independent of i and usually >0.9 .

the Moon [Keihm, 1984; Hayne et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2021]. The emissivity spectra derived from Salisbury et al. [1987] exhibit a weak spectral contrast and thus produce a high $\bar{\epsilon}_h$. The lunar analogs and the spectra of Donaldson Hanna et al. [2017] who measured Apollo emissivity spectra under ambient and simulated lunar conditions have a stronger spectral contrast and yield slightly lower $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ -values. This experiment indicates that the bolometric-hemispherical emissivity of the Moon is likely between $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.90 \dots 0.95$ and hardly depends on the incidence angle i , generally agreeing with the literature.

3.2 Hermean case

Figure 2 (left) shows the $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ for $r = 0.30$ AU, which corresponds to Mercury’s distance at perihelion. The $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ -values are consistently lower compared to the $r = 1$ AU-case. Further, the bolometric emissivity strongly depends on the incidence angle. Higher incidence angles cause higher emissivity values. This effect is comparatively strong and must be considered for any scenario of Mercury, and it is not possible to neglect the value, such as Emery et al. [1998] do. The dependency on the incidence angle effect has never been modeled in planetary science literature. Here, a simple empirical relationship is proposed

$$\bar{\epsilon}_h = 1 - a \cos^{\frac{1}{2}}(i), \quad (13)$$

where $a = 0.22$ for the hermean perihelion and $a = 0.15$ for aphelion. Future studies must generalize these findings. A smaller bolometric-hemispherical emissivity of Mercury causes the equilibrium temperature to rise and the

The experiment shows that the bolometric-hemispherical emissivity of Mercury is significantly lower than that of the Moon, probably even below $\bar{\epsilon}_h < 0.8$, and depends on the incidence angle i . The low $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ -values lead to a higher equilibrium temperature than expected from a constant $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.9$ or $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.95$.

Figure 2. Left: Bolometric-hemispherical emissivity $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ of a surface covered in regolith of various compositions. At perihelion, the surface is $r = 0.30$ AU away from the Sun and illuminated under different incidence angles i . $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ becomes significantly lower and strongly depends on i . Right: Same as left but for aphel with a solar distance of $r = 0.46$ AU.

4 Conclusion

The experiments show that the common assumption of a constant bolometric-hemispherical emissivity of $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.90 \dots 0.95$ holds for the Moon. However, this value cannot simply be assumed for Mercury. The experiments indicate that Mercury's bolometric emissivity depends on the incidence angle i and might be even lower than $\bar{\epsilon}_h < 0.8$. A low bolometric emissivity significantly increases the equilibrium temperature and must thus be considered for any temperature study of Mercury. Future studies are needed to quantify this value precisely.

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